

Mentoring Health Science Library Students in a Regional Health Information Outreach Program

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ABSTRACT

There are numerous knowledge areas and abilities needed to be successful in a health sciences librarianship career, but many master's programs lack curriculum coverage of this subspecialty. Mentorship programs can address professional pathway and competencies gaps for those seeking advanced degrees or continuing education in any field. This is especially true in health sciences librarianship and can help dispel misconceptions that a background in science is necessary, or that employment is only in academic or hospital settings.

The Network of the National Library of Medicine (NNLM) Region 4 employed formal and informal theoretical methods to mentor future health sciences librarians by guiding students in a leadership role for a real-life project. Projects had a core focus of increasing access to health information, but sought to address gaps in the students' curriculum related to health sciences librarianship. Projects touched on public health, community outreach; diversity, equity, and inclusion; and content creation. Students engaged with their mentors one-on-one and in group meetings, and worked on creating a scholarly work tied to their project that could be published in a professional journal, or presented at a professional conference. As an organization, the NNLM has been successful in completing these goals while the students were actively enrolled in their graduate library science programs. Formal evaluation was accomplished through channels both at the students' universities and the NNLM.

INTRODUCTION

Health sciences librarianship is a fairly new subspecialty in the United States even though the first American school of librarianship opened in 1887 (Columbia University Libraries, 2019). The necessary knowledge and abilities needed to succeed in a health sciences librarianship career include leadership and management, resources management, technology management, curriculum design and instruction, and an understanding of scientific research methods. As the health sciences specialization continues to grow in need, employment of medical librarians is expected to increase 34% by 2030 (United States Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2022). But currently only 40% of the 64 institutions offering American Library Association (ALA)-accredited Master's Programs in Library and Information Studies offer health sciences librarianship or health informatics in the curriculum (American Library Association, 2022). Many of these programs have very few courses addressing the breadth of skills needed in the subspecialty.

Developing the skills, knowledge, and abilities to be successful in health sciences librarianship is challenging. Baseline competencies have been identified by library associations, employers, and those working in health care. Lawton et al. (2014) found ten common areas of competence: communication, systematic review, critical appraisal, managing and organizing health information, managing and organizational skills, training and education, legal, leadership, technology, and understanding the healthcare environment. Mentorship programs can address professional pathway and competencies gaps for those seeking advanced degrees or continuing education in any field. This is especially true in health sciences librarianship and can help dispel misconceptions that a background in science is necessary, or that employment is only in

academic or hospital settings. Ennis et al. (2010) found over a decade ago that the majority of health sciences librarians ended up in their career accidentally. This is still the case with many library science undergraduate and graduate programs lacking a health sciences track. It might also explain a survey finding that that one in seven health sciences librarians experienced imposter phenomenon (Barr-Walker et al., 2019). This phenomenon can cause feelings of inflated perceptions of one's abilities and a fear of being evaluated (Mak et al., 2019). A successful mentorship can help build skills and address any self-doubts or insecurities a student might harbor.

Koos et al. (2020) found that only 40% of health sciences librarians in the U.S. and Canada responding to a survey were interested in health sciences librarianship when starting their graduate programs. Mentorship programs focused on health sciences librarianship can bridge the gap for students wanting to explore and gain experience in this specialization. Bartley et al. (2021) noted that building or improving core professional skills in health sciences librarianship could be accomplished with a mentorship. The Network of the National Library of Medicine Region 4 developed a mentorship program to provide students with project leadership experience and the support system of a mentor and a regional outreach staff who shared a common interest in health sciences librarianship.

SETTING

The Network of the National Library of Medicine (NNLM) is an outreach program coordinated by the National Library of Medicine (NLM) since 1965 and implemented through a nationwide network of seven regions, several offices and centers, and membership from numerous health science libraries and information centers. The mission of the NNLM is to advance the progress of medicine and improve the public health by providing all U.S. health professionals with equal access to biomedical information and improving the public's access to information to enable them to make informed decisions about their health. Regional offices are staffed with master's degree or higher specialists who work in communities to improve access to health information. Specialists encourage community-level networking and collaboration, provide training on NLM health information resources, and manage outreach awards.

Student engagement is an NLM and National Institutes of Health (NIH) priority area for NNLM as a way to advance their shared missions. The NNLM offers a variety of health information access-related activities intended to be of interest to a broad range of students. Activities are designed to accommodate student schedules, locations, and personal goals.

NNLM Region 4, administered out of the University of Utah, serves Arizona, Colorado, Idaho, Montana, New Mexico, North Dakota, South Dakota, Utah, and Wyoming. Due in part to the Covid-19 pandemic and to the rural nature of the region, a variety of in-person and virtual mentoring opportunities are available to participants. The Region 4 mentorship program champions health sciences librarianship by developing partnerships with Library and Information Science (LIS) and other graduate programs, collaborating with undergraduate programs,

professional associations (like MLA), and other organizations to work toward increasing diversity in the LIS pipeline, and mentorship.

METHODOLOGY

Several theories and models were used to engage students and ensure both mentors and students received a quality experience when working on a project. The basis of all of our mentorship comes from the works of Lev Vygotsky (Theory of Cognitive Development [Moore, 2011]) and Albert Bandura (Social Learning Theory [Bandura, 1977]). The Theory of Cognitive Development and the Social Learning Theory allowed participants to learn from one another and make the program rewarding for both. Within these theoretical foundations, some specific models and theories were highlighted in the program: Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (Silverman, 2011) emphasizes the relationship between mentor and student and the feedback loop that enhances both party's skills. Within the Social Learning Theory, the primary focus is on modeling/observational learning. The students observe and then model/practice quality health librarianship.

Students applied for consideration in the regional program to work on a specific project with the program specialists and administrators who all are MLIS/MLS-trained librarians. During the first weeks of their internship, they were acclimated to the region and our program. They then began working on a special project in the area of health science librarianship. Students met regularly online with their mentor and received guidance from their academic institution's internship advisors to ensure they were making progress on their projects as well as achieving the goals of their internship program. Students attended regional staff online meetings and shared questions and or findings discovered while working on projects. A unique expectation of the program is that students present their projects at a professional conference or publish a peer-reviewed journal article on their experiences. This helps them learn the art of scholarly tone and writing and provides an additional artifact for their professional dossier.

RESULTS

Completed student projects focused on diversity, equity, and inclusion; community outreach; and developing instruction and resources for diverse populations. Professional competencies developed over the course of the projects included communication, critical appraisal, organizational skills, leadership, and technology.

- The DEI Survey investigated diversity and inclusion activities by member libraries in the former MidContinental Region (MCR) of the NNLM. Two MLIS students worked with Region 4 staff and a consultant to conduct an environmental scan of library programming addressing issues of diversity and inclusion. The students presented at a professional conference and contributed to an article on the survey findings.

- The Proximity Mapping project utilized spatial thinking and the social psychology principle of proximity to understand the geographical relationship among libraries, public health departments, and community-based health organizations. Two MLIS students worked with Region 4 staff to learn and populate an online mapping tool. The students contributed to several conference presentations at several conferences, a white paper, and an article on the project.
- The Health Information Leadership project generated health information resources for the student's local community. Three MLIS students developed programs on vaccine information in Spanish with English translation for a national program to engage underrepresented communities in biomedical research.
- A project connecting LGBTQ+ students, faculty, staff and community members to health information and resources was carried out by one MLIS student. The student designed the layout and vetted resources for a LibGuide hosted on the academic library's website.

DISCUSSION

The regional program has a history of successful mentoring opportunities for graduate library and information studies students. With established principles and procedures, students and mentors have reported positive experiences and have been able to use the projects to advance their skills and professional development in the field of health science librarianship. The primary goal of the program was to provide real-life opportunities for students interested in the health sciences.

The Region 4 mentorship program relies heavily on established theoretical foundations and established practices to ensure the best possible outcomes for both the students and the mentors. We hope to continue outreach and engagement with student mentees to assist in filling the need for highly trained health science information professionals. Future exploration includes employing metrics to understand if the types of projects offered by Region 4 address gap areas and how they contributed to a student's success in their professional careers.

ENDNOTES

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